
Development of a Control Technique of Active Power Filter

A Thesis Submitted by

Eng. Abdellatif Mohammed Abdellatif Aboutaleb

In Partial Fulfilment of the Degree of M.SC.

In
Electrical Engineering

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Abdellatif Mohammed Aboutaleb

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ABSTRACT

The tendency of connecting the Power Electronic loads and distributed power plants through Power Electronic converters is increasing day by day. These Electronic converters and loads are the sources of harmonics and reactive power. Also the presence of single-phase loads in the 3-phase distribution systems causes many problems in the distribution and transmission systems. This is because of the unbalanced current drawn by the unbalanced loads. These two problems greatly affect the performance of the power system network, and reduce the system power quality.

Due to the rapid development in power electronic devices and state-of-the-art electronic circuit technology, the active power filters (APFs) have been developed and put into practical applications. The APF can solve problems of harmonic and reactive power simultaneously. APF can also be used to compensate the unbalance in the three-phase load currents and make the grid supplies only the positive-sequence components of the load currents only.

APFs are still expensive due to high switching operation of its switches. Many efforts are done in recent years to reduce the number of the APF switches from six switches to four switches. This reduces the overall cost of APF, but DC-link of APF must be modified by splitting the capacitor to two capacitors and the capacitor Mid-Point acts as the third leg of the inverter. And then the different control schemes must be also modified to control the two DC-link capacitor voltages through controlling only four-switch inverter.

This thesis is mainly divided into two main sections. The first section introduces a four-switch three-phase shunt APF (FSTP-APF) based on one cycle control (OCC) technique for compensating the currents of three phase non-linear. The power stage of FSTP-APF uses only four semiconducting switches which lead to reduce the overall cost of APF. The proposed technique retains the advantages of the conventional OCC, such as no reference current calculation, no need to use phase-locked loop (PLL), very simple control circuit and constant switching frequency. In addition the modification

reduces the number of semiconductor switches, reduces the filter output inductances, reducing the number of sensors to only four sensors, two of them for measuring supply currents and the others for measuring DC-link voltages, and the control algorithm becomes simpler. The feasibility and performance of the proposed technique are demonstrated through the simulation and experimental verifications.

The power stage of shunt APF used to compensate non-linear unbalance 3-phase loads is of two types; Four-leg APF and Split capacitor APF.

The second section introduces a split-capacitor APF based on synchronous reference frame theory (SRF) for compensating the currents of 3-ph 4-wire unbalance non-linear loads. Two modifications are done in reference currents calculations using SRF. The first one is to modify the DC-link voltage control loop to control two voltages across two capacitors on the DC-link; this is done to make them constants at a certain value for the correct operation. The second one is that the SRF zero-sequence current is included in reference currents calculation to compensate the unbalance in currents in the supply side. The current controller used is the hysteresis current control due to its simplicity and fast response in controlling the filter currents. The advantages of the modification is to make the supply see the unbalanced non-linear load with SAPF as a linear balanced load at point of common coupling (PCC), and The current controller becomes simpler containing only three current loops, and lower number of sensors and semiconductor switches are used. The mathematical analysis is done to modify the DC-link voltage control. The system performance is verified through simulation studies using MATLAB/SIMULINK. An experimental setup is implemented to validate the system performance actually.

List of Symbols and Abbreviations

APF	Active Power Filter
FSTP	Four Switch Three Phase
SSTP	Six Switch Three Phase
OCC	One Cycle Control
SRF	Synchronous Reference Frame
IRPT	Instantaneous Reactive Power Theorem
SVPWM	Space Vector Pulse Width Modulation
TCPWM	Triangular Comparison Pulse Width Modulation
PLL	Phase-Locked Loop
PCC	Point Of Common Coupling
ZSC	Zero Sequence Current
SC-APF	Spilt-Capacitor Active Power Filter
FL-APF	Four-Leg Active Power Filter

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INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Electrical energy is the most efficient and popular form of energy and the modern society is heavily dependent on the electric supply. The life cannot be imagined without the supply of electricity. At the same time the quality of the electric power supplied is also very important for the efficient functioning of the end user equipment.

The term power quality became most prominent in the power sector and both the electric power supply company and the end users are concerned about it [1]. The quality of power delivered to the consumers depends on the voltage and frequency ranges of the power. If there is any deviation in the voltage and frequency of the electric power delivered from that of the standard values then the quality of power delivered is affected.

Now-a-days with the advancement in technology there is a drastic improvement in the semi-conductor devices. With this development and advantages, the semi-conductor devices got a permanent place in the power sector helping to ease the control of overall system. Moreover, most of the loads are also semi-conductor based equipment. But the semi-conductor devices are non-linear in nature and draws non-linear current from the source. And also the semi-conductor devices are involved in power conversion, which is either AC to DC or from DC to AC. This power conversion contains lot of switching

operations which may introduce discontinuity in the current. Due to this discontinuity and non-linearity, harmonics are present which affect the quality of power delivered to the end user. In order to maintain the quality of power delivered, the harmonics should be filtered out. Thus, a device named *Filter* is used which serves this purpose.

1.2 LITERATURE REVIEW

To overcome the problems caused by harmonics, filters are used as shown in Fig. 1.1. Early passive filters are used for harmonic elimination for a certain load, but passive filters cannot adapt themselves to any change in the grid or load impedances. Active power filters (APF) [2]-[4] are widely used to eliminate the harmonics from the line currents and supply voltages at the point of common coupling (PCC) and adapt itself with any change in load or grid impedances, this is done by controlling the DC-link voltage of the APF inverter to get the required compensating currents overcoming the disadvantages of passive ones.

The main problem of APF is its cost due to the high switching of the inverter switches. To make APF more cost-efficient, the current rating of APF should be reduced through using a passive filter to compensate the fundamental reactive current and the APF is only used to compensate only the harmonics at PCC [5]-[8].

APF is divided into two main types, shunt and series APF [9]-[11]. The shunt APF is used for current compensation by injecting the required compensating currents at PCC, and the series one is used for voltage compensation.

Current reference calculation is a main part of conventional control circuits of APF. The main purpose of these calculations is to get the desired reference currents. The reference currents mainly are the harmonics of the load currents only or with reactive components of the load currents. The most common

techniques used for reference current calculations are synchronous reference frame (SRF) [12],[13] and instantaneous reactive power theory (IRPT) [14],[15].

Fig. 1.1 basic operation of filters

The calculations using SRF only need the load currents and don't require any voltage signal, so any distortion in the grid voltage cannot affect the calculation, but it requires using phase-locked loop (PLL) that increases the robustness of the control scheme. Calculation using IRPT doesn't require the use PLL, but has two main disadvantages; the first one is that the control algorithm requires a complicated structure for implementing. The second disadvantage is

that the reference currents calculation depending on the supply voltages as pure sinusoidal waves, so any distortion in the supply voltages affects directly the currents calculations, and then the operation of the APF is not in the correct manner.

The above calculations for the reference currents depending on the load current, direct current control algorithms is different because it depends on the source currents,[16] it is divided into two main types: current-source-based and balance-power-based.

Several schemes are used to control the APF output currents to make it follow the reference ones such as, hysteresis current control [17], variable parameter pulse width modulation (PWM) [18], space vector PWM [19] and many other techniques.

There are other techniques that don't require any reference current calculations; one of them is one-cycle-control (OCC) technique [20], [21]. OCC has many advantages such as, simplicity of the control circuit, no need for control circuit that calculate the reference currents and constant switching frequency for the semiconductor switches, but this control scheme has a disadvantage that this scheme cannot differentiate between the harmonic and reactive currents which leads to raising the current rating of the switches. This scheme is modified to compensate only the harmonic current, and the APF based on OCC become pure harmonic compensator [22].

Conventional three-phase APF power stage consists of 3-leg, each leg contains two semiconductor switches, and a capacitor in the DC-side of APF. A four-switch three-phase (FSTP) APF has been studied by replacing one leg of six-switch three-phase (SSTP) APF by two capacitors [23]-[24]. FSTP-APF has fewer switches when compared with SSTP-APF which leads to decreasing the overall cost of APF for low-cost application and make the control algorithms simpler.

Many efforts are exerted in recent years to modify APF control algorithms to be suitable for controlling the switches of FSTP-APF to compensate load currents [25]-[26].

In addition to the problem of the existence of the non-linear loads, there is another problem in the networks due to the presence of single-phase loads in the 3-ph systems. The difference in the impedances of the single-phase loads leads to make the current drawn from the supply unequal then the source currents become unbalance [27], [28]. The unbalance in currents drawn from the source leads to many problems such as: decreasing the power system efficiency and voltage unbalance at the loads terminals due to the difference in the voltage drops in the grid impedances. The voltage unbalance at the 3-ph loads causes many problems such as increasing the 3-ph motor losses, and power system stability problems

Many researches works on using APF to make the supply seeing the 3-ph unbalance non-linear loads as balanced linear loads [29], [30]. In this case the APF is used to compensate the load negative and zero-sequence currents in addition to the harmonic components of load currents. Then the network supplies only the fundamental positive sequence currents of the load currents.

1.3 FILTER types

In general, filters are classified into three basic types. They are Active Filters, Passive Filters and Hybrid filters. Each type has its own sub classification. Fig. 1.2 shows the detailed classification of the filters.

1.3.1 Passive Power Filters:

These filters consist of passive elements like capacitor, inductor and resistor. These are widely used because of their low cost and ease of control. The passive filters also provide reactive power apart from filtering the harmonics.

The performance of these filters is heavily dependent on the system impedance. These are again classified into two types- low pass and high pass.

Fig. 1.2 classification of the filters.

A. Low Pass Filter:

The low pass filter is a tuned LC circuit that is tuned to provide low impedance for a particular harmonic current. In addition these filters are also used for power factor correction. In power system network they are generally used to filter 5th and 7th order harmonics. The line diagram of the low pass filter is shown in Fig. 1.3.

B. High Pass Filter:

The high pass filters are also made of passive elements like inductor and capacitor but show low impedance for harmonic current above a particular corner frequency. All the harmonics present above that corner frequency are filtered

using this filter. This filter is again of many types like first-order, second-order, and third-order etc., based on the number of passive filters used in it. Among them the second order filter is widely used. Fig. 1.4 shows the line diagram of a high pass filter.

Fig. 1.3. low pass filter

Fig. 1.4. high pass filter

But there are some disadvantages with passive filter, like-

- The filter characteristics has strong dependence on the system impedance
- Possibility of over load in the passive filter because of harmonic current circulation generating from power electronic loads

- The change of the load impedance can detune the filter, so it is not suitable for variable loads
- The problem of series and/or parallel resonances can be originated which causes instable operation
- Limited operation, that is used to eliminate either a particular order or fewer harmonics
- Component aging

Because of the above disadvantages the passive filters cannot provide an effective solution to enhance the quality of the power system. Thus, the active power filters are employed to overcome the above drawback.

1.3.2 Active Power Filters (APF):

To overcome the drawback of passive filter, active compensation known as Active Power Filter is used recently. The APF is a Voltage Source Inverter (VSI) which injects the compensating current or voltage based on the network configuration. It was proposed around 1970. But the recent advancement in power electronics technology [31], along with the theory of instantaneous active and reactive power which was presented in 1983, APFs are an up-to-date solution with fast switching devices, low power loss and fast digital processing devices at an affordable price. Depending on the circuit configuration and function, APFs are divided into three types and each one is explained in detail below.

A. Shunt Active Power Filter:

The voltage sourced inverter based Shunt APF is similar to STATCOM. It is connected in shunt at the PCC. It injects the current which is equal and opposite to the harmonic current. It acts as a current source injecting harmonics and is suitable for any type of load. It also helps in improving the load power factor. The circuit diagram of the power system with shunt connected APF is shown in Fig. 1.5. The cost of these filters is relatively higher and so not preferred for large scale systems.

Fig. 1.5 Circuit Diagram of Shunt active power filter

B. Series Active Power Filter:

As the name indicates, these filters are connected in series with the line through a matching transformer. This filter injects the compensating voltage in series with the supply voltage. Thus, it acts as a voltage source which can be controlled to compensate the voltage sag/swell. These filters have their application mainly where the load contains voltage sensitive devices. The circuit diagram of the power system with series connected APF is shown in Fig. 1.6. These filters are not used practically since they are required to handle high current ratings which increase the size of the filter as well as the losses occurring in the filter.

C. Unified Power Quality Conditioner (UPQC):

The UPQC is a combination of series and shunt active power filters. It has the advantage of both series APF and shunt APF. That means, it compensates both the voltage and current harmonics. Therefore, this filter can compensate

almost all types of power quality problems faced by a power system network [32]. The circuit diagram of power system with UPQC is shown in Fig. 1.7.

Fig1.6 Circuit Diagram of Series active power filter

Fig1.7 Circuit Diagram with UPQC

1.3.3 Hybrid Power Filters:

The active power filters are better solution for power quality improvement but they require high converter ratings. So to overcome this drawback, hybrid power filters are designed. The hybrid power filters are the combination of both

active and passive power filters. They have the advantage of both active and passive filters. There are different hybrid filters based on the circuit combination and arrangement. They are-

- Shunt Active Power Filter and Series Active Power Filter
- Shunt Active Power Filter and Shunt Passive Filter
- Active Power Filter in series with Shunt Passive Filter
- Series Active Power Filter with Shunt Passive Filter

Each filter configuration is explained below with their merits and demerits.

A. Shunt APF and Series APF:

Fig1.8 Shunt APF and Series APF Combination.

This filter combination has the advantage of both series connected APF i.e., elimination of voltage harmonics and that of shunt connected APF of eliminating current harmonics. The circuit diagram is shown in Fig. 1.8. This combination finds its application in Flexible AC Transmission Systems (FACTS). But the control of APF is complex and this combination involves two APF and hence the control of this filter configuration is even more complex. Thus, this filter combination is not used widely.

B. Shunt APF and Shunt Passive Filter:

The power rating of the APF depend on the order of frequencies it is filtering out. Thus, an APF used for filtering out low order harmonics have low power rating with reduced size and cost. This logic is used in designing this filter combination. The shunt connected APF filters out the low order current harmonics while the shunt connected passive filter is designed to filter out the higher order harmonics. The circuit configuration of this filter topology is shown in Fig. 1.9.

Fig1.9 Shunt APF and Shunt Passive Filter Combination

But the main disadvantage of this filter configuration is it cannot be suited for variable loading conditions. Since, the passive filter can be tuned only for a specific predetermined harmonic.

C. APF in Series with Shunt Passive Filter:

In this filter configuration, the Active Power Filter is connected in series with a Shunt connected Passive Filter. The circuit diagram of this filter configuration is shown in Fig. 1.10. The advantage of this configuration is that the passive filter reduces the stress on the power electronic switches present in the APF. This filter has its application in medium to high voltage ranges.

Fig1.10 APF in series with Shunt Connected Passive Filter

D. Series APF with Shunt Connected Passive Filter:

The Series APF and Shunt APF combination seen in Fig. 1.9 has the problem of complex control strategy. To overcome this drawback, the shunt APF is replaced by a shunt connected passive filter. The passive power filter does not require any additional control circuit and the cost is also less. This filter combination is shown in Fig. 1.11.

Here the series connected APF provides low impedance (almost zero) for low frequency components whereas the shunt connected APF provides less impedance for high frequency components and filters out all higher order harmonics. So this filter configuration is the most beneficial of all others and has the advantage of reducing both current and voltage harmonics. Thus [33], in this project this filter configuration is used for the improvement of electric power quality.

Fig1.11 Series APF with Shunt Connected Passive Filter

1.4. THESIS OBJECTIVES

There are two main objectives of this thesis:

- The first objective is to present a four-switch three-phase active power filter (FSTP-APF) based on OCC technique, the inverter consists of four semiconducting switches in two legs to compensate the currents of two phases. The third leg consists of two capacitors with the mid-point is connected to the third phase to compensate its current. The control circuit is modified to control the dc voltage across two capacitors through controlling only 4 switches. The analysis of FSTP-APF, modification of the control circuit, simulation results, experimental results and conclusion are demonstrated in chapter 2.
- The second objective; a split-capacitor shunt active filter is used at a point in a 4-wire 3-ph nonlinear unbalanced system to compensate the load-side harmonics, negative sequence and zero sequence components of load currents, this is done to reduce the grid-side unbalance and harmonics on the grid line currents to the minimum

values as possible. SRF is used to calculate the reference currents; the DC-link voltage control loop is modified to control the voltages of the two capacitors in the DC-link instead of controlling one capacitor voltage. Hysteresis current control is used to control the filter output currents. The modeling of the 3-leg split-capacitor APF, voltage control loop modification, simulation and experimental studies are illustrated in chapter 3.

1.5. Thesis Outline

The thesis is organized as follows;

Chapter 1

This chapter introduces a literature review for some previous work, types of filters, and the object of this thesis.

Chapter 2

This chapter introduces the operation principles of four-switch three phase APF (FSTP-APF). In addition, this chapter proposes a modification in one cycle control technique to make it suitable for controlling FSTP-APF. The mathematical analysis, simulation studies, and experimental verifications are introduced.

Chapter 3

This chapter introduces the three-phase four-wire APF used in compensating three-phase non-linear unbalanced loads. In this chapter, two modifications are done in reference currents calculations using SRF. The first one is to modify the DC-link voltage control loop to control two voltages across two capacitors on the DC-link; this is done to make them constants at a certain value for the correct operation. The second one is that the SRF zero-sequence current is included in reference currents calculation to eliminate the neutral

current and compensate the unbalance in currents in the supply side. The current controller used is the hysteresis current control due to its simplicity and fast response in controlling the filter currents.. The mathematical analysis, simulation studies, and experimental verifications are introduced.

Chapter 4

This chapter offers the conclusions of the present work and the future work that can be performed on the same object.

A Four-Switch Shunt Active Power Filter Based on One Cycle Control for Compensating the Currents of Three-Phase Non-Linear Load.

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Shunt APFs are widely used for eliminating the load currents harmonics from the supply currents. APF is still expensive due to high switching operation. The inverter of APF consists of six semiconductor switches with a capacitor in the DC-link. In low power applications, the FSTP-APF is a cost-efficient due to the reduced number of switches in the inverter forming two legs, in this type two capacitors are used in the DC-link forming the third leg.

In this chapter a FSTP-APF based on OCC is introduced. The control circuit is modified to control the voltages of the capacitors in the DC-link.

FSTP-APF based on the modified OCC technique retains the advantages of conventional Six-Switch 3-Phase APF with the conventional OCC technique. A comparative study is done to show the superior of this system to the other techniques. This study is summarized in table 2.1. This study shows that the FSTP- APF based on OCC requires the minimum possible number of sensors with the conventional OCC applied to 6-switch APF, but the proposed scheme

has less number of semiconductor switches than the conventional one. Also the proposed scheme doesn't require any current calculation and no need for PLL in the control circuit which make the control circuit simple and robust. Also this scheme can compensate the reactive components beside the harmonics components of the load currents. Also one important feature of this control scheme is that the switching frequency is constant, which leads to minimize the switching losses.

TABLE. 2.1. Comparison of different schemes

scheme	Use of PLL	Number of sensor	Need for current calculation	Compensation
SRF method	YES	10	YES	HRC*
IRPT method	YES	10	YES	HRC
CS method	YES	10	YES	HC*
PB method	YES	7	NO	HC
OCC method	NO	4	NO	HRC
FSTP-APF with the proposed OCC scheme	NO	4	NO	HRC

*harmonic and reactive current compensation (HRC), *harmonic compensation only (HC).

2.2 MODELING OF 3-LEG AND 2-LEG SHUNT APF

A 3-leg shunt APF is shown in Fig. 2.1. In this topology, the return path of a current in a particular leg is established through the two other legs of the inverter.

So, it is not possible to analyze the 3-leg topology as a 3 individual single phase inverter topology.

Fig. 2.1. 3-leg shunt APF power circuit.

There are 12 switching states possible for the operation of the 6 switches in the 3-leg inverter at which, when one switch of the two of a certain leg is in the ON state, the other will be off.

The modeling equations [35] of the 3-leg inverter APF is as follow,

$$3L_{fa} \frac{di_{ca}}{dt} = (S_1X - S_2Y)V_c - 3i_{ca}R_{fa} - 3V_{sa} \quad (2.1)$$

$$3L_{fb} \frac{di_{cb}}{dt} = (S_3X - S_4Y)V_c - 3i_{cb}R_{fb} - 3V_{sb} \quad (2.2)$$

$$3L_{fc} \frac{di_{cc}}{dt} = (S_5X - S_6Y)V_c - 3i_{cc}R_{fc} - 3V_{sc} \quad (2.3)$$

Where $X = S_2 + S_4 + S_6$. $Y = S_1 + S_3 + S_5$. S_1 , S_3 and S_5 are the switching pulses of the top switches, and their values vary between 0 and 1, the value 0 represents the off-state of the switch, 1 represents the ON-state of the

switch. V_c is the DC-link voltage, $L_{fa}, R_{fa}, L_{fb}, R_{fb}$ and L_{fc}, R_{fc} are the equivalent series parameters of the output filter inductors. i_{ca}, i_{cb} and i_{cc} are the compensation currents taken from filter of phase A,B and C sequentially.

If one leg of SSTP-APF is replaced by two capacitors, then the total number of switches is reduced to only four switches. The switching states are also reduced to only 8 for the operation of FSTP-APF. The modeling equations of FSTP-APF become any two equations of depending on the leg to be replaced.

In Fig. 2 the leg of phase C is replaced by two capacitors then the modeling equations of this case is as follow based on [35],

$$2L_{fa} \frac{di_{ca}}{dt} = (S_1 X V_{c1} - S_2 Y V_{c2}) - 2i_{ca} R_{fa} - 2V_{sa} \quad (2.4)$$

$$2L_{fb} \frac{di_{cb}}{dt} = (S_3 X V_{c1} - S_4 Y V_{c2}) - 2i_{cb} R_{fb} - 2V_{sb} \quad (2.5)$$

$$\frac{di_{cc}}{dt} = C_1 V_{c1} + C_2 V_{c2} \quad (2.6)$$

Where V_{c1}, V_{c2} are the DC-voltages of the upper and lower capacitors sequentially. $X = S_2 + S_4$, and $Y = S_1 + S_3$.

2.3 FOUR SWITCH THREE PHASE APF TOPOLOGY

The FSTP-APF replaces the third leg of three-phase APF by two split capacitors C1, C2 as shown in Fig. 2.2. The non-linear load is balanced then,

$$i_{ia} + i_{ib} + i_{ic} = 0 \quad (2.7)$$

$$i_{sa} + i_{sb} + i_{sc} = 0 \quad (2.8)$$

The compensation currents must be also balanced for correct operation of the FSTP-APF. The following derivation confirms that if we only use two legs of three-phase APF to compensate the currents of two phases and replace the third leg with two capacitors with the mid-point connected to the third phase then, the midpoint gives the current required to compensate the third phase without any control. This enables us to reduce the number of semiconductor switches and simplify the control algorithm. But any control

scheme must be modified to control the voltage of the DC-link capacitors for the correct operation of FSTP-APF.

Fig. 2.2. Circuit diagram of FSTP APF

Using Kirchoff current law (KCL) at Gaussian curve M as shown in Fig. 2 then,

$$i_{ca} + i_{cb} = i_{c1} + i_{c2} \tag{2.9}$$

Applying KCL at capacitor midpoint then,

$$i_{c1} + i_{c2} = i_c \tag{2.10}$$

Combining equations (7), (8) then we find,

$$i_{ca} + i_{cb} = i_c \tag{2.11}$$

From Fig. 2, the direction of the current entering the capacitor midpoint is in opposite direction with phase-C compensating current then,

$$i_{cc} = -i_c \quad (2.12)$$

Combining equation (9) with equation (10) then we can find

$$i_{ca} + i_{cb} + i_{cc} = 0 \quad (2.13)$$

The previous analysis shows that, while compensating the currents of two phases using FSTP APF of three-phase non-linear load, the third leg compensate the current of the third phase.

2.4 FSTP APF BASED ON OCC

The control goal of APF based on OCC is to make the supply seeing the load with APF as a pure resistive load, so the current of the supply is sinusoidal and in phase with the input voltage. The conventional control equations of OCC is as follow,

$$\begin{aligned} R_s \cdot i_{sa} &= V_m \cdot (1 - 2 \cdot k_a) \\ R_s \cdot i_{sb} &= V_m \cdot (1 - 2 \cdot k_b) \\ R_s \cdot i_{sc} &= V_m \cdot (1 - 2 \cdot k_c) \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

Where R_s is the current sensor gain, i_s is the source current, V_m is the output of the proportional integral (PI) which control the error between actual DC link voltage and the reference one, and K is the duty ratio for the semiconductor switches.

The control equations must be modified in order to control the two capacitors voltages by controlling only two legs of the shunt APF inverter.

From Fig. 2, let's assume that k_a , k_b is the duty ratio for the semiconductor switch in the lower portion of the inverter legs, and $(1 - k_a)$, $(1 - k_b)$ is the duty ratio for the semiconductor in the upper portion of the inverter. Due to high switching of semiconductor switches, then the

instantaneous value of v_{AN} , v_{BN} is considered constant during one switching cycle. The average value of v_{AN} , v_{BN} in terms of duty ratio and DC link voltages is as follow,

$$v_{AN} = V_{c1} * (1 - k_a) - V_{c2} * (k_a) \quad (2.15)$$

$$v_{BN} = V_{c1} * (1 - k_b) - V_{c2} * (k_b) \quad (2.16)$$

Modifying equations (2.13), (2.14) then,

$$v_{AN} = V_{c1} - k_a * (V_{c1} + V_{c2}) \quad (2.17)$$

$$v_{BN} = V_{c1} - k_b * (V_{c1} + V_{c2}) \quad (2.18)$$

The value of the filter inductances is small, then we can neglect the line frequency voltage drops across them for the sake of analysis [36], so,

$$v_{AN} = v_{sac} \quad (2.19)$$

$$v_{BN} = v_{sbc} \quad (2.20)$$

Combining equations (2.17), (2.18) with equations (2.19), (2.20) respectively, then,

$$v_{sac} = V_{c1} - k_a * (V_{c1} + V_{c2}) \quad (2.21)$$

$$v_{sbc} = V_{c1} - k_b * (V_{c1} + V_{c2}) \quad (2.22)$$

The supply at the point of common coupling (PCC) sees the load with shunt APF as a pure resistive load, then,

$$v_{sac} = R_e * i_{sac} \quad (2.23)$$

$$v_{sbc} = R_e * i_{sbc} \quad (2.24)$$

Where R_e is the equivalent resistance of the non-linear load and the shunt APF. Combining equations (2.21), (2.22) with equations (2.23), (2.24) respectively, then ,

$$R_e * i_{sac} = V_{c1} - k_a * (V_{c1} + V_{c2}) \quad (2.25)$$

$$R_e * i_{sbc} = V_{c1} - k_b * (V_{c1} + V_{c2}) \quad (2.26)$$

Multiplying both sides of equations (2.25), (2.26) by R_s/R_e , then we find,

$$R_s * i_{sac} = V_{m1} - V_{m2} * k_a \quad (2.27)$$

$$R_s * i_{sbc} = V_{m1} - V_{m2} * k_b \quad (2.28)$$

Where $V_{m1} = (V_{c1} * R_s / R_e)$, and $V_{m2} = (V_{c1} + V_{c2}) * (R_s / R_e)$, so we can get V_{m1} from a PI controller, controlling the error between V_{c1} and V_{c1}^* , and V_{m2} from a PI controller, controlling the error between the actual value of the DC link voltage and the reference one. So the control circuit is modified to control the two midpoint capacitors to maintain their voltages equal.

By using a resettable integrator to achieve the control goal equations (2.27),(2.28) as follow [26]. V_{m1}, V_{m2} are constant values depending on V_{c1}, V_c respectively, so they can easily be calculated by controlling the errors between the actual and reference values of the DC-Link voltages V_{c1} and V_c using a PI controllers. But k_a, k_b are not constant, they change during each switching cycle to make the FSTP-APF able to eliminate the harmonics and reactive components of load currents. To generate the values of $(k_a * V_{m2}), (k_b * V_{m2})$ in the control algorithm then, a resettable integrator is then use to integrate the value of V_{m2} during the ON-period of the lower switches as in equations (2.29),(2.30).

$$R_s * i_{sac} = V_{m1} - \frac{1}{T_i} * \int_0^{k_a * T_s} V_{m2} dt \quad (2.28)$$

$$R_s * i_{sbc} = V_{m1} - \frac{1}{T_i} * \int_0^{k_b * T_s} V_{m2} dt \quad (2.29)$$

Due to high switching for semiconductor switches, so V_{m1} and V_{m2} may be considered unchangeable, putting the integrator constant T_i equal to the switching period T_s [18], then equations (2.27), (2.28) are converted to the new control equations (2.29), (2.30). The block diagram for the proposed control technique is shown in Fig. 2.3.

Fig. 2.3. Proposed control circuit of FSTP-APF based OCC.

2.5 FSTP-APF PARAMETER DESIGN

Correct selection of FSTP-APF is so important to guarantee the correct operation of the filter. However, bad selection of the parameters may cause many problems in the grid. FSTP-APF parameters included DC-Link voltage, DC-Link capacitors, switching frequency, and filter AC-side inductors.

- DC-link voltage selection

Proper DC-link voltage is required for effectively tracking the reference filter current and to bring the percentage THD of the source current within acceptable limits. Many efforts are done to deduce an empirical formula for the DC-link voltage [37],[38], with considering the practical limitation of this voltage. It is found that if the DC-link voltage equal to 1.6 of the maximum

value of the phase voltage, the THD of the supply current decreases to the most acceptable value.

$$V_{DC} = 1.6 * V_m \quad (2.31)$$

Where V_{DC} is the DC-link voltage, and V_m is the maximum value of the phase voltage. In split capacitor topologies, there are two capacitors in the DC-link, for the correct operation, each capacitor voltage must equal the value given by the above equation, so the total DC-link voltage become twice in the value [25].

- DC capacitor selection

The design of the DC capacitors value depends on the load transient or voltage sag/swell in the system and its ability to regulate the DC link voltage under these conditions. The value of the DC capacitor is given by the following equation [37],[38].

$$C = \frac{2(X_{\max} - X_{\min})nT}{V_{DC\max}^2 - V_{DC\min}^2} \quad (2.32)$$

Where X is the KVA rating of the system, X_{\max} and X_{\min} are the maximum and minimum values of the load KVA change during transient conditions respectively. $V_{DC\max}$ and $V_{DC\min}$ are the maximum and minimum values of the capacitor change during transient conditions respectively. n is the transient cycle number, and T is the period of the supply voltage. After choosing the capacitor value in μF , then the voltage rating and ripple current rating of the capacitors must be taken into account.

The current ripple rating of the capacitors can be deduced from the following equation[39].

$$I_r > \sqrt{\left(\frac{I_1}{K_{f1}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{I_2}{K_{f2}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{I_3}{K_{f3}}\right)^2 + \dots} \quad (2.33)$$

Where K_{fx} , $x=1,2,3,\dots$ is the frequency factors [27], I_x , $x=1,2,3,\dots$ is the components of the capacitor current at frequencies f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots , and I_r is the

ripple current rating of the capacitor.

- Switching frequency

The OCC technique has a good feature that the switching frequency is constant. Increasing the switching frequency leads to reduce the distortion. However this increases the switching loss and requires high rating semiconductor switches, which increase the cost of the filter [22]. So choosing the switching frequency depends on two factors, cost of the filter and the required compensated THD of the load currents.

- Filter AC-side inductor

AC-side inductances are main components of APFs, it works on shaping the filter compensation currents, and reduces the ripples in the filter current. So proper selection of their values are so important [40]. In [40], A simulation study is done to determine the effect of changing L value, the conclusion of this study is that, for an APF there is a value for the inductance at which the minimum value of THD of the supply current is achieved, above or lower this value, supply current distortion increases. So it is important to choose the value of the inductances that brings the distortion in the supply current to its lower value. Also current rating of these inductors must be taken into account. Following the selection of the filter parameter, the controllability range of the FSTP-APF is checked. Initially, the system modeling equations (2.4), (2.5), and (2.6) are rearranged to obtain the FSTP-APF state space model.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{i}_{ca} \\ \dot{i}_{cb} \\ \dot{i}_{cc} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-R_{fa}}{L_{fa}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-R_{fb}}{L_{fb}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} * \begin{bmatrix} i_{ca} \\ i_{cb} \\ i_{cc} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-1}{L_{fa}} & 0 & \frac{S_1 X}{2L_{fa}} & \frac{S_2 Y}{2L_{fa}} \\ 0 & \frac{-1}{L_{fb}} & \frac{S_3 X}{2L_{fb}} & \frac{S_4 Y}{2L_{fb}} \\ 0 & 0 & C_1 & C_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{sa} \\ v_{sb} \\ V_{C1} \\ V_{C2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.34)$$

In state space form equation (2.34) can be rewritten as:

$$\dot{X} = AX + BU \quad (35)$$

Comparing (2.34) with (2.35) then

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-1}{L_{fa}} & 0 & \frac{S_1 X}{2L_{fa}} & \frac{S_2 Y}{2L_{fa}} \\ 0 & \frac{-1}{L_{fb}} & \frac{S_3 X}{2L_{fb}} & \frac{S_4 Y}{2L_{fb}} \\ 0 & 0 & C_1 & C_2 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-R_{fa}}{L_{fa}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-R_{fb}}{L_{fb}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.36)$$

Then the controllability matrix is as follow,

$$\mathbf{M} = [\mathbf{B} \quad \mathbf{AB} \quad \mathbf{A}^2\mathbf{B}] \quad (2.37)$$

The system controllability can be checked for the chosen values of parameters, using rank of the M matrix. Moreover, the choice of the control parameters is important to assure system stability over a wide range of harmonics. This enables the APF to work properly achieving the claimed functions such as making constant capacitors voltages. To demonstrate the stability of the FSTP-APF based on the modified OCC, bode plot is required, the following transfer function of the proposed topology is obtained as:

$$\text{T.F} = \frac{(2K_P)S^2 + (K_P K'_I - 2K_I)S + K_I K'_I}{TS^3 + (1 + 2K_P)S^2 + (K_P K'_I - 2K_I)S + K_I K'_I} \quad (2.38)$$

Where K_P, K_I are the proportional and integral gains of the PI controllers respectively, K'_I is the gain of the resettable integrator, and T is the inverter time delay. Based on the above equation the bode-plot is obtained shown in Fig. 2.4, which assures system stability in controlling the DC-link voltages.

Fig. 2.4. Bode-plot of the system

2.6 SIMULATION RESULTS

MATLAB/SIMULINK is applied to confirm the performance of FSTP-APF based on OCC technique. The system parameters in the simulation studies are provided in table II based on the design equations illustrated in section V.

The load used in the simulation studies is a three-phase diode rectifier with R-L load. The currents drawn by the load shown in Fig. 2.5, are distorted due to the non-linearity nature of the load. The harmonic spectrum of Phase-C load current is as illustrated in Fig. 2.6, it is clear that the THD of Phase-C load current is 30.84%.

When FSTP-APF is connected at PCC, The DC voltage across C1 and the total DC-link voltage across the two capacitors are built to reach the reference values. The DC-link voltages are as illustrated in Fig. 2.7. At the instant that the DC-link voltages reaches the reference values then, the FSTP-APF injects currents equal but opposite to the harmonic currents required by the load to compensate the supply currents. The simulation results of FSTP-APF compensation currents are shown in Fig. 2.8.

After compensating, the supply currents are reshaped to be sinusoidal after the harmonic current injected by the FSTP-APF. Fig. 2.9 demonstrates the currents in the supply side. The THD of the Phase-C supply current become 1.91 using simulated harmonic spectrums shown in Fig. 2.10.

To study the ability of the FSTP-APF with the modified OCC in compensating the load reactive currents with the load current harmonics, a 3-ph inductive load with $L = 50$ mH per phase is connected in parallel with the non-linear load described in Table 2.2. As shown in Fig. 2.11, the FSTP-APF compensates the harmonics and reactive components of the load current. the power factor in Fig. 2.11, is improved from 0.33 up to approximately unity in the supply side.

TABLE. 2.2. Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Simulation Values
Supply Voltage	220V/50HZ
Filter Inductance	8mH
Dc Side Capacitor	2200 μ f
Switching Frequency	12.8KHZ
Integrator gain	12800
Dc Link Voltage references	Vc1*=660V, Vc*=1320V
PI Determining Vm1	Kp=0.4, ki=20
PI Determining Vm2	Kp=0.4, ki=20
Load Resistance	80 Ω
Load Inductance	6mH

Simulation studies have been done to investigate the performance of the proposed scheme during dynamic conditions of startup and step change in the load. Fig. 2.12 shows the transient performance when the FSTP-APF is applied. From this figure it is obvious that the supply currents are equal to the distorted load current before instant of startup. At the instant of application, the source currents increase during a small transient period to charge the DC-link capacitors up to the reference value, The DC-link capacitors voltages before connecting FSTP-APF is not equal to the desired (reference) value, that is because the capacitor voltage control loop depends on connecting APF to PCC to draw the required currents from the grid to keep DC-link capacitors voltages at the required value for the correct operation of APF. So at the moment of startup,

high charging currents are drawn from the grid to raise the capacitor voltage up to the required value. when the capacitors built their voltage to the reference value, then the APF currents become equal to the reactive, harmonic components of the load currents and a small active current to keep the DC-link voltages constants at the reference values to guarantee the best operation of FSTP-APF in compensating load currents. So the source currents becomes only the fundamental active current required by the load plus a small active current for compensation the FSTP-APF capacitors losses.

Fig. 2.5. The simulated results of load currents. (a) Phase-A load currents. (b) Phase-B load current. (c) Phase-C load current.

Fig. 2.6. The simulated results of the harmonic spectrum of the Phase-C load currents.

Fig. 2.7. The simulated results of DC-capacitor voltages. (a) DC voltage across C1. (b) DC voltage across C2. (c) Total DC-link voltage.

Fig. 2.8. The simulated results of APF compensating currents. (a) Phase-A compensating currents. (b) Phase-B compensating current. (c) Phase-C compensating current.

Fig. 2.9. The simulated results of supply currents after compensation. (a) Phase-A supply currents. (b) Phase-B supply current. (c) Phase-C supply current.

Fig. 2.10. The simulated results of the harmonic spectrum of the Phase-C supply currents.

Fig. 2.11 Simulated study of compensating harmonics and reactive component of the load currents. (a) phase-B voltage. (b) phase-B load current. (c) phase-B compensating current. (d) phase-B source current.

Fig. 2.12. The simulated results of phase-C currents when FSTP-APF based on OCC is applied. (a) Phase-C load currents. (b) Phase-C compensation currents. (c) Phase-C supply current.

Fig. 2.13. The simulated results of phase-C currents and the total DC-link voltage during load change. (a) Phase-C load currents. (b) Phase-C source currents. (c) total DC-link voltages.

To investigate the simulation performance of FSTP-APF during load change, the load is changed from $R_1 = 80\Omega$, $L_1 = 6\text{mh}$ to $R_1 = 40\Omega$, $L_1 = 3\text{mh}$. Fig. 2.13 shows that the proposed FSTP-APF based on OCC adapt itself to the load variations.

Simulations studies are done to investigate up to what distortion in the load current can the FSTP-APF work to decrease the distortion in the supply current to acceptable levels. To be able to change the THD of the load current, a controlled rectifier with R-L load in the DC-side is used. By changing the firing angle, then the THD of the load is changed. At different firing angles, both THDs of the load and supply currents are measured at $4700\mu\text{F}$ capacitors in the DC-side of FSTP-APF. Fig. 2.14 shows a plot of THD of the load current with THD of source current at constant values of the capacitors. From Fig. 2.14, at $C_1=C_2=4700\mu\text{F}$ up to 63% distortion in the load current, FSTP-APF with the modified OCC can eliminate the supply current distortion to acceptable levels.

Fig. 2.14. THD of the load current with THD of the source current at $C_1=C_2=4700\mu\text{F}$

To study the effect of the capacitors value in supply distortion, a simulation study is done at 34% load distortion as shown in Fig. 2.15. From this figure, it is obvious that with increasing the capacitances values, supply current distortion decreases. So increasing the capacitances increases the ability of the FSTP-APF

to compensate load currents with higher distortion. But increasing the capacitance values in μF deteriorates the transient performance of the system.

Fig. 2.15. Source current distortion with varying the DC-Link capacitances values.

The controllability of the system is checked using the controllability matrix illustrated in equation (2.36). The controllability matrix contains the system parameters and the switching states, using the chosen parameter shown in table II and the possible switching state, then a four controllability matrices are then deduced. It is found that the rank of each M is equal to the rank of B which indicates that the system is fully controllable.

2.7 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS.

To study the actual performance of FSTP-APF, reshown in Fig. 2.3, experimentally, a setup of the system is implemented as illustrated in Fig. 2.16. The experimental setup consists of an inverter of four IGBTs. Two IGBTs modules type MITSUBISHI CM100DY-24H are used to form the two leg of the inverter. The DC-link of the inverter consists of two DC capacitors of $2200\mu\text{F}$ each.

The four IGBTs form two legs of the inverter and are connected to PCC through a two inductive filter whose equivalent series parameters are $L_f =$

8mH, $R_f = 0.3\Omega$ with 15A rating. The DC-link capacitors midpoint forms the third leg connected directly to the third phase. Simulation studies indicate that, the capacitor current ripples is 1.7A, so suitable capacitor is then choosing from [27]. The power supply is a three phase auto-transformer adjusted at standard value 220 Vrms per phase 50 Hz. The load is formed through a 3-ph bridge rectifier with series R-L load in the DC-side whose parameters are $R_l = 80\Omega$, $L_f = 6\text{mH}$. The rated power of the load resistor is 5 KW, and the rated current of the load inductance is 15A. The control system is consists of a MPC 8240 digital signal processor dSPACE (DS-1104) with PPC 603e core. The processor is clocked at 250 MHz.

Two current sensors LA25-NP are used to measure the source currents of two phases and sent to dSPACE (DS-1104) platform via analog to digital converters. The upper capacitor and the total DC-link voltage are measured using two voltage sensors LV25-P. The voltage signals are sent to the voltage control loops and the result of this loop is compared with the two current control loops in order to control the duty ratio of the pulses sent to the gates of the four semiconductor switches in order to make the DC-link voltages equal to the reference values and to get the required compensating currents. An interface circuit is used to amplify the drive pulses power taken from dSPACE (DS-1104) to a higher power level suitable for driving the gates of FSTP-APF inverter, and isolate the control system from the power circuit.

As illustrated in Fig. 2.17, the non-linear load draws currents of non-sinusoidal shape containing harmonics, if the APF is not connected at the load terminals, the grid currents supplied to the load will equal to the load currents, and this may cause many problems in the grid. The load harmonic spectrum is shown in Fig. 2.18.

The proposed FSTP-APF based on OCC is implemented and then is connected to main PCC at the load terminals and then studying the actual performance of the system.

Fig. 2.19 shows the DC-link voltages, it is clear that the voltages of upper capacitor and the total DC-link voltages follow the reference values, so the voltages across the two capacitor is the same higher than the peak of the supply voltages and equal to the half of the total DC-link voltages. When the capacitor voltages reach the desired values, then the FSTP-APF injects the compensating currents which equal and opposite to the harmonics and reactive components of the load currents. The compensation currents are demonstrated in Fig. 2.20.

Fig. 2.16. A top view of the experimental setup of the system.

The grid supplies only the fundamental active current. The experimental results of the supply currents are as illustrated in Fig. 21 and Fig. 2.22. Source current FFT plot illustrated in Fig. 2.23, shows that the THD of the supply current decrease to 4.16%

Experimental studies are done to examine the actual operation of FSTP-APF based on OCC during load changes to investigate its performance during transient operation. Fig. 2.24 illustrates the good performance of the proposed FSTP-APF to any change in the load whether the load increases or decreases. Fig. 2.25 and Fig. 2.26 show the experimental FFT plot of the load and supply currents during step change respectively.

Figs. 2.16-2.26, confirm the experimental performance of the proposed FSTP-APF based on OCC technique for compensating the currents of three-phase non-linear load.

Fig. 2.17. Experimental results of load currents drawn by the three-phase rectifier.

(a) Phase-A load currents. (b) Phase-B load current. (c) Phase-C load current.

Fig. 2.18. Experimental harmonic spectrum of the Phase-C load currents.

Fig. 2.19. Experimental results of the DC-link voltages. (a)DC voltage across C1. (b) DC voltage across C2. (c) Total DC-link voltage.

Fig. 2.20. Experimental results of the compensating currents supplied by the filter.
(a) Phase-A compensating current. (b) Phase-B compensating currents. (c) Phase-C compensating current.

Fig. 2.21. Experimental results of the supply currents. (a) Phase-A source current. (b) Phase-B source currents. (c) Phase-C source current.

Fig. 2.22. Experimental results of the supply currents.

Fig. 2.23. Experimental harmonic spectrum of the Phase-C source currents.

Fig. 2.24. Experimental results of phase-C current during load changing. (a) Phase-C load current when the load increases. (b) Phase-C source current when the load increases. (c) Phase-C load current when the load decreases. (d) Phase-C source current when the load decreases.

Fig. 2.25. Experimental harmonic spectrum of the load current after load change.

Fig. 2.26. Experimental harmonic spectrum of the supply current after load change.

2.8 CONCLUSION.

In this chapter a FSTP-APF based on OCC has been introduced. OCC scheme has been modified to control the two capacitor voltage in the DC-Link. FSTP-APF based on one OCC has many advantages such as; cost reduction due to the reduced number of switches, simpler control algorithm, no need for reference current calculations and no need of PLL in the control. The performance of FSTP-APF based on OCC has been validated through simulation and experimental studies.

Split-Capacitor Shunt Active Filter for Compensating Harmonics and unbalance in Three-Phase Four-Wire Systems

3.1 INTRODUCTION

In this chapter, a split capacitor shunt APF (SC-APF) is introduced. This APF is used to compensate 3-Ph 4-W nonlinear unbalance loads. SRF theorem is used for currents reference calculations; it is modified to control two capacitors in the DC-Link. Hysteresis current control is used due to its simplicity and fast response performance, simulation and experimental studies are done to validate the performance of this filter.

3.2 APF POWER INVERTER FOR 3-PH 4-WIRE SYSTEMS.

The inverter of the APF used for 3-ph 4-wire systems is one of two types, Four-leg APF (FL-APF) and SC- APF as demonstrated in Fig. 3.1, and Fig. 3.2, Sequentially[37].

The advantages of the FL-APF is that the DC-link voltage is the half of its counterpart in split-capacitor topology and then the voltage stress on each switch is reduced.

SC-APF power circuit gives many advantages over the FL-APF such as, reduction in the number of switches and simpler control circuit

Fig. 3.1. FL-APF power circuit.

3.3 MODELING OF 4-LEG AND SPILT CAPACITOR SHUNT APF USED 3-PH 4-WIRE SYSTEMS

The switches of the APF inverter operate in a way that the APF injects the compensating currents to point of common coupling (PCC) and to maintain the capacitor voltage constant at the reference value. The drive circuit gives the

pulses in a random way to achieve the above conditions under a constrain that any two switches in any leg must be not on the ON-state at the same time [38].

FL-APF reshown in Fig. 3.1 contains 8 switches. So there are 24 switching states, then the modeling of this topology is described by the following equations [26].

Fig. 3.2, SC- APF power circuit

$$4L_{fa} \frac{di_{fa}}{dt} = (S_1X - S_2Y)V_c - 4i_{fa}R_{fa} - 4v_{sa} \quad (3.1)$$

$$4L_{fb} \frac{di_{fb}}{dt} = (S_3X - S_4Y)V_c - 4i_{fb}R_{fb} - 4v_{sb} \quad (3.2)$$

$$4L_{fc} \frac{di_{fc}}{dt} = (S_5X - S_6Y)V_c - 4i_{fc}R_{fc} - 4v_{sc} \quad (3.3)$$

$$4L_{fN} \frac{di_{fN}}{dt} = (S_7X - S_8Y)V_c - 4i_{fN}R_{fN} \quad (3.4)$$

Where $X = S2 + S4 + S6 + S8$, $Y = S1 + S3 + S5 + S7$. $S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6, S7, \text{ and } S8$ are the states of the switches and equal to 0 and 1 when the switch is on the ON-state and OFF-state respectively. (l_{fa}, R_{fa}) , (l_{fb}, R_{fb}) , (l_{fc}, R_{fc}) , and (l_{fN}, R_{fN}) are the filter equivalent series parameters connected to phases a, b, c, and neutral respectively. i_{fa}, i_{fb}, i_{fc} and i_{fN} are the filter currents injected to PCC. V_c is the DC-link capacitor voltage.

SC-APF used in 3-phase 4-wire systems reshown in Fig. 3.2 contains 6 switches, then the number of the total switching states for the APF inverter is 12. The following equations describe the modeling of this topology under the different switching states[26].

$$3L_{fa} \frac{di_{ffa}}{dt} = (S_1 X V_{c1} - S_2 Y V_{c2}) - 3i_{fa} R_{fa} - 3V_{sa} \quad (3.5)$$

$$3L_{fb} \frac{di_{ffb}}{dt} = (S_3 X V_{c1} - S_4 Y V_{c2}) - 3i_{fb} R_{fb} - 3V_{sb} \quad (3.6)$$

$$3L_{fc} \frac{di_{ffc}}{dt} = (S_3 X V_{c1} - S_4 Y V_{c2}) - 3i_{fc} R_{fb} - 3V_{sc} \quad (3.7)$$

Where $X = S2 + S4 + S6$ and $Y = S1 + S3 + S5$.

3.4 GENERAL DESCRIPTION FOR APF CONTROL TECHNIQUE.

The concept of shunt APF control technique is to be a current control circuit such as, hysteresis current control, space vector pulse width modulation, and triangular comparison pulse width modulation. These control techniques need current references which equal to the line currents harmonics if it needs to compensate the current harmonics only or equal to the harmonics plus reactive components of the line current if it needs to make the power factor at the point of common coupling (PCC) unity. The reference currents can be calculated by many

methods such as synchronous reference frame (SRF) and instantaneous reactive power theory (IRPT).

From the previous discussion, the convention of the APF control circuit is to be of two parts, the first part is to calculate the reference currents, and the second part is to control the filter output current[44]. This is as shown in Fig. 3.2.

Fig. 3.3. Convention of the APF control circuit.

3.5 REFERENCE CURRENT CALCULATIONS ADJUSTMENT TO INCLUDE THE UNBALANCE COMPONENTS OF THE LOAD CURRENTS.

The basic calculation algorithm of SRF is shown in Fig. 3.4 The 3-Ph load currents are measured then transformed into dq-frame through the following equations.

$$i_d = \bar{i}_d + \tilde{i}_d = \frac{2}{3} (\sin(\theta) \cdot i_{1a} + \sin\left(\theta - \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot i_{1b} + \sin\left(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot i_{1c}) \quad (3.8)$$

$$i_q = \bar{i}_q + \tilde{i}_q = \frac{2}{3} (\cos(\theta) \cdot i_{1a} + \cos\left(\theta - \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot i_{1b} + \cos\left(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot i_{1c}) \quad (3.9)$$

Where i_{1a} , i_{1b} , and i_{1c} are the 3-Ph load currents, i_d , i_q are the load currents components in the dq-frame, \bar{i}_d and \tilde{i}_d are the DC and AC components of i_d , where \bar{i}_d represents the fundamental active components of the load currents and \tilde{i}_d represents the harmonic active components of the load currents, \bar{i}_q and \tilde{i}_q are the DC and AC components of i_q , where \bar{i}_q represents the fundamental reactive components of the load currents and \tilde{i}_q represents the harmonic reactive components of the load currents, and θ represents the grid voltage position.

To generate the reference currents that include the harmonics and reactive components of the load currents then a High-Pass Filter (HPF) is used to eliminate \bar{i}_d then the reference currents in the 3-ph can be calculated from the following equations.

$$i_{fa}^* = \sin(\theta) \cdot \tilde{i}_d + \cos(\theta) \cdot i_q \quad (3.10)$$

$$i_{fb}^* = \sin\left(\theta - \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot \tilde{i}_d + \cos\left(\theta - \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot i_q \quad (3.11)$$

$$i_{fc}^* = \sin\left(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot \tilde{i}_d + \cos\left(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot i_q \quad (3.12)$$

Fig. 3.4, Block diagram for calculating compensating currents using SRF.

If the 3-Ph load currents are unbalanced then the reference currents must contain the unbalance components of the load currents this is done by calculating the zero-sequence current in SRF by the following equation.

$$i_0 = \frac{1}{3}(i_{1a} + i_{1b} + i_{1c}) \quad (3.13)$$

Then the reference currents calculated in (3.10),(3.11) and (3.12) are modified to contain the unbalance components of the load current as follow,

$$i_{fa}^* = \sin(\theta) \cdot \tilde{i}_d + \cos(\theta) \cdot i_q + i_0 \quad (3.14)$$

$$i_{fb}^* = \sin\left(\theta - \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot \tilde{i}_d + \cos\left(\theta - \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot i_q + i_0 \quad (3.15)$$

$$i_{fc}^* = \sin\left(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot \tilde{i}_d + \cos\left(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot i_q + i_0 \quad (3.16)$$

The block diagram that shows the above calculations is as shown in Fig. 4

Fig. 3.5, Block diagram for calculating reference currents which include the harmonic plus unbalance components of the load currents using SRF.

3.6 DC-LINK VOLTAGE CONTROL

During the operation of APF, the DC-Link voltage decreases due to the losses in the switching and in the DC-link capacitor, so it is required to draw an

active current from the grid to compensate these losses and to guarantee that the DC-Link voltage is constant at the appropriate value, so the reference current equations are modified to,

$$i_{fa}^* = \sin(\theta) \cdot (\tilde{I}_d - \overline{I_{cap}}) + \cos(\theta) \cdot i_q + i_o \quad (3.17)$$

$$i_{fb}^* = \sin\left(\theta - \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot (\tilde{I}_d - \overline{I_{cap}}) + \cos\left(\theta - \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot i_q + i_o \quad (3.18)$$

$$i_{fc}^* = \sin\left(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot (\tilde{I}_d - \overline{I_{cap}}) + \cos\left(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot i_q + i_o \quad (3.19)$$

Where $\overline{I_{cap}}$ is the active value of the current in SRF that compensate the APF losses, and can be obtained from the voltage control loop shown in Fig. 5. And the minus sign of $\overline{I_{cap}}$ indicates that the direction of these currents are in the opposite direction of the filter currents illustrated in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. The above equations are suitable for FL-APF because in this topology, one capacitor is used in the DC-link.

The DC-Link of SC-APF contains two capacitors, so the challenge in this topology is to modify the above equations to be suitable for controlling the two capacitors voltages. The modified reference currents equations are as follow;

$$i_{fa}^* = \sin(\theta) \cdot (\tilde{I}_d - \overline{I_{cap1}} - \overline{I_{cap2}}) + \cos(\theta) \cdot i_q + i_o \quad (3.20)$$

$$i_{fb}^* = \sin\left(\theta - \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot (\tilde{I}_d - \overline{I_{cap1}} - \overline{I_{cap2}}) + \cos\left(\theta - \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot i_q + i_o \quad (3.21)$$

$$i_{fc}^* = \sin\left(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot (\tilde{I}_d - \overline{I_{cap1}} - \overline{I_{cap2}}) + \cos\left(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi\right) \cdot i_q + i_o \quad (3.22)$$

Where $\overline{I_{cap1}}$ and $\overline{I_{cap2}}$ are the active values of the currents in SRF that compensate the APF losses and control the two capacitors voltages in the DC-Link. To obtain these currents two DC-link voltage control loops are implemented as demonstrated in Fig. 6.

Fig. 3.6. DC-Link voltage control for FL-APF

Fig. 3.7. Proposed DC-Link voltage control for SC-APF.

3.7 HYSTERESIS CURRENT CONTROL.

Several methods are used to control the currents of shunt APF such as hysteresis current control as it is the simplest way to control the current as shown in Fig. 3.8. The hysteresis current control changes its output state depending on comparing the error signal with upper and lower limits of the controller.

The output of the controller controls the switches of one leg to control its current to make it follows the reference value of the current. One of the most advantages of using hysteresis current control is that the response of the controller is so fast but its only disadvantage is that the switching frequency is not constant causing an increase in switching losses.

Researchers work on reducing the switching losses of hysteresis current controller by making the band of the controller variable in a certain manner, and is not constant as convention [45], [46].

Fig. 3.8, Hysteresis current control.

3.8 SIMULATION RESULTS.

MATLAB/SIMULINK has been used to test and study the operation of the proposed control system. The power system reshown in Fig. 3.2, reference current calculation demonstrated in Fig. 3.3, and current controller shown in Fig. 3.7, are implemented. The control goal is to keep the APF capacitors voltages equal and regulated at a certain value higher than the peak of supply voltages to ensure a good control performance of the APF. The unbalance load is designed using star-connected three single-phase rectifiers with different values of the load resistances and inductances. The system parameters and controllers gains used in the simulation studies are provided in table 3.1.

TABLE. 3.1. Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Simulation Values
Supply voltage (ph-ph)	230 V_{rms}
DC-link voltage references	$V_{c1}^* = 690V$, $V_{c2}^* = 690V$, and $V_c^* = 1380V$
APF Filter inductance	8 mH
DC-link capacitors	4700 μF
Load parameters	$R_a = 16\Omega, L_a = 24 mH,$ $R_b = 21\Omega, L_b = 18mH$ $R_c = 12.5\Omega, L_c = 20 mH$
PI gains for two voltage control loops	$k_i = 0.4,$ $k_p = 8$

Fig. 3.9, shows the load currents. It is obvious that the three phase currents are distorted and unbalanced. The unbalance in currents equal 15%, and

the THD for phase-A equal 22.43% as illustrated in Fig. 3.10. Before applying spilt-capacitor APF, the source currents equal the load currents.

When spilt-capacitor APF is connected to main PCC then, the capacitors on the DC-link build their voltages to reach the reference values, the DC-link voltages are shown in Fig. 3.11.

When the DC-link voltages reach their correct values determined by the reference ones. Then APF injects the required compensating currents. The phase compensating currents contain the negative value of the load currents harmonics, and components responsible for the unbalance in the load currents, so the summation of filter currents equal but opposite to the neutral current at the capacitor mid-point. Fig. 3.12 shows filter phase currents.

The supply currents become the fundamental positive sequence currents as illustrated in Fig. 13. The harmonics spectrum of the supply currents is shown in Fig. 3.14, the THD decreases to 1.98% and the unbalance in the supply side decreases to 1.68%.

Simulation studies are done to test the operation of the spilt-capacitor APF when a 3-ph inductive load of 50mH is connected in parallel with the previous unbalanced, non-linear load. The calculation circuit is modified to make the reference currents contain the reactive components of the load currents so the supply currents become in-phase with the supply voltage, then the power factor is corrected. This is illustrated in Fig. 3.15. If the control circuit is adjusted to make the reference currents compensate only load current harmonics with unbalance components of the load currents, then the source currents contain the fundamental component of load currents. This is demonstrated in Fig. 3.16.

From Fig. 3.15, and Fig. 3.16. If the reactive current is compensated, then the filter current would be larger than its current if the reactive current is not compensated. So it is preferred to apply APF to compensate only the harmonics

with unbalance components of the load currents to reduce the switches current rating.

To study the performance of the split-capacitor APF with the proposed control technique during transient conditions, simulation studies are done to verify the good performance of APF during startup and load change. Fig. 3.17 shows phase-A currents during the application of APF at $t = 1\text{sec}$.

A step change is done in the loads to increase currents. Fig. 3.18 shows the fast response of the proposed APF to 100% load changes.

Fig. 3.9. Simulated results of the load currents. (a) Phase-A load current. (b) Phase-B load current. (c) Phase-C load current.

Fig. 3.10. Harmonic spectrum of phase-A load current.

Fig. 3.11. Simulated results of DC-link voltages.

Fig. 3.12. Simulated results of the filter phase currents. (a) Phase-A compensating current. (b) Phase-B compensating current. (c) Phase-C compensating current.

Fig. 3.13. Simulated results of the supply currents. (a) Phase-A supply current. (b) Phase-B supply current. (c) Phase-C supply current.

Fig. 3.14. Harmonic spectrum of phase-A source current.

Fig. 3.15. Simulated results of phase-A voltages and currents when APF compensates load reactive currents. (a) Phase-A supply voltage. (b) Phase-A supply current. (c) Phase-A load current. (d) Phase-A filter current.

Fig. 3.16. Simulated results of phase-A voltages and currents when APF doesn't compensate load reactive currents. (a) Phase-A supply voltage. (b) Phase-A supply current. (c) Phase-A load current. (d) Phase-A filter current.

Fig. 3.17. Simulated results of the phase-A currents during APF startup. (a) Phase-A load current. (b) Phase-A supply current. (c) Phase-A filter current.

Fig. 3.18. Simulated results of the phase-A currents during 100% load variation. (a) Phase-A load current. (b) Phase-A supply current. (c) Phase-A filter current.

3.9 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS.

To study the actual performance of the split-capacitor APF with the proposed control circuit in compensating the harmonics and unbalanced components of the load currents. An experimental setup as shown in Fig. 3.19 is implemented. The system consists of 3-ph auto-transformer acts as the 3-ph supply. The unbalanced load consists of three 1-ph bridges, 3 resistances of 5KW rating are used and are adjusted at 16Ω , 21Ω and 13Ω connected to the DC-link of the bridges of phase-A, phase-B, phase-C respectively. The load inductances are adjusted at $24mH$, $18mH$, and $20mH$.

Three modules of MITSUBISHI CM100DY-24H IGBTs are used to form the 3-leg of the inverter. Two capacitors of $4700\mu F$ are used in the APF DC-link, with the mid-point connected directly to neutral at PCC to compensate its

current. Three inductances acts as filter output inductances, the equivalent series parameters for each are $L_f = 8mH$, $R_f = 0.3\Omega$.

The control system is consists of a MPC 8240 digital signal processor dSPACE (DS-1104) with PPC 603e core. The processor is clocked at 250 MHz .

Five LA25-NP current sensors are used to measure the currents and send them to dSPACE (DS-1104) platform via analog to digital converters. Two of them for measuring the phase-A, and phase-B filter currents for the current controllers, and the others are used for measuring the load currents for reference currents calculations. Two LV25-P voltage sensors are used for measuring the DC-link capacitors voltages for the voltage control loops.

An interface circuit is used to amplify the power and the voltage of the IGBTs pulses taken from dSPACE (DS-1104) platform, and to isolate the control system from the power system.

Fig. 3.19. Experimental setup for examining the actual operation of the SC-APF.

As seen in Fig. 3.20, the currents drawn by the load are distorted and unbalanced. If these currents are drawn from the supply, the harmonic and unbalance components would cause many problems in the power system.

The split-capacitor APF with the modified control circuit is then connected to main PCC. The capacitors voltages build their voltages up to the reference values; this is demonstrated in Fig. 3.21. When DC-link voltages reach their steady state values, then the APF injects the compensating currents shown in Fig. 3.22. These currents compensate the harmonic and unbalance components of the load phase currents. Then the supply currents actually become only the fundamental positive-sequence components of the load currents. Then the split-capacitor APF makes the supply seeing the non-linear unbalanced load with it as a linear balanced load. The supply currents are as illustrated in Fig. 3.23.

The load neutral current is compensated through the DC-link mid-point. The neutral currents are shown in Fig. 3.24. It is clear that the neutral current in the supply side decreases experimentally to the standard levels.

Fig. 3.20. experimental results of the load currents. (a) Phase-A load current. (b) Phase-B load current. (c) Phase-C load current.

To study the transient performance of spilt-capacitor shunt APF with the proposed control circuit, a step-change is done in the load. The equivalent series R-L parameters of the unbalance load are $(32\Omega, 48\text{ mH})$, $(42\Omega, 36\text{ mH})$ and $(25\Omega, 40\text{ mH})$ connected to the DC-side of the load rectifiers connected to phase-A, phase-B, and phase-C respectively. A step-change is done to increase the load by 40% in each phase, the load parameters after the load change become $(16\Omega, 24\text{ mH})$, $(21\Omega, 18\text{ mH})$ and $(12.5\Omega, 20\text{ mH})$ respectively. The load currents during step-change are shown in Fig. 3.24.

Fig. 3.26 shows the experimental source currents. It is clear from this figure that the spilt-capacitor APF with the proposed control scheme is adapted to the load variation.

Fig. 3.21. Experimental results of the DC-link voltages.

Fig. 3.19, to Fig. 3.26, validate the actual performance of the SC-APF with the proposed control circuit to compensate the 4-Wire, 3-Phase unbalance non-linear loads.

From the above sections, the SC-APF for compensating unbalance non-linear has been introduced, the simulated and actual performance of this filter has been also validated.

Fig. 3.22. Experimental results of the filter phase currents. (a) Phase-A compensating current. (b) Phase-B compensating current. (c) Phase-C compensating current.

Fig. 3.23. Experimental results of the supply currents. (a) Phase-A supply current. (b) Phase-B supply current. (c) Phase-C supply current.

Fig. 3.24. Experimental results of the neutral currents. (a) Phase-A supply current. (b) Phase-B supply current. (c) Phase-C supply current.

Fig. 3.25. Experimental results of the load currents during 40% load change.

Fig. 3.26. Experimental results of the source currents during 40% load change.

3.10 CONCLUSION.

In this chapter, SC-APF based on SRF has been introduced. The modifications in SRF to be able to generate the reference currents for SC-APF has been discussed. The voltage control loop has been modified to control the DC-link capacitors voltages. This scheme with the modified control algorithm can compensate the harmonics, reactive, and unbalance components of the 3-Ph unbalanced non-linear loads. The superior of this scheme is to compensate the unbalanced nonlinear loads with many advantages over the other used topologies such as, the proposed APF with the proposed control technique is cost-efficient due to the lower number of switches, inductances and sensors, and the calculations are not affected by the grid voltages. Table 3.2 provides a comparison between this scheme and the other used topologies and shows the superior of the proposed scheme.

TABLE 3.2. The superior of SC-APF based on SRF

scheme	Effect of the grid voltage in calculation	Number of semiconductor switches	Number of current sensors for calculations	Number of filter inductances
SC-APF based SRF	NO	6	6	3
FL-APF based on SRF	NO	8	8	4
FL-APF based on IRPT	YES	8	8	4

Conclusions and Future Work

4.1. CONCLUSIONS

The demand for electric power is increasing at an exponential rate and at the same time the quality of power delivered became the most prominent issue in the power sector. Thus, the reduction of harmonics, improving the power factor of the system, and reducing unbalance in the network current is of utmost important. In this project a solution to improve the electric power quality by the use of Active Power Filter is discussed. From the study of Active Power Filter for power quality improvement the following conclusions are drawn in this thesis:

In chapter 2: A FSTP-APF based on OCC to compensate non-linear loads is explored. This scheme has many advantages such as reducing the number of switches, reducing the number of filter output inductors, only two current sensors are required, no need for using PLL and that control algorithm is simpler than the control scheme for other types of control algorithms. From the analysis, we can find that if we control only two legs of the APF inverter, and replace the semiconductor switches of the third leg by two capacitors, the current from the capacitors mid-point compensate the current of the third phase. Analytical studies are made to modify the conventional OCC to make it suitable for controlling only the switches of two legs and controlling the DC voltages across the two DC-link capacitors. The aim of these modifications is to keep the two capacitors voltages equal in magnitude and each equal to the half of the total DC-link voltage. To evaluate the performance characteristics of the proposed

scheme, simulation studies have been done using MATLAB/SIMULINK, and experimental studies are confirmed by implementing a laboratory platform.

In chapter 3: a split-capacitor shunt APF based on synchronous reference frame has been demonstrated for compensating 3-ph non-linear unbalanced loads. Analytical studies have been done to modify the reference currents calculations to control the two capacitors voltages in the DC-link. Simulation studies have been done to verify the operation of the proposed APF. Actual performance has been confirmed experimentally through an experimental setup. The APF introduced in this chapter provides many advantages, such as: it can compensate the load currents of 4-Wire 3-Phase unbalance non-linear load with simpler control circuit, less number of switches, lower number of sensors when it is compared with four-leg APF topology. Simulation studies have done using MATLAB/SIMULINK. Also experimental setup has been implemented to validate the performance of the proposed system.

4.2. FUTURE WORK

The work done in this thesis can be further extended such new improvements can be found. The feasible options are-

- ❖ Modifying the other possible control techniques to make it suitable for controlling FSTP-APF.
- ❖ Exert efforts to make these modification suitable for series APF.

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

- [1] Abdellatif M. Aboutaleb, Haitham Z. Azazi, Dina S. M.Osheba, and Awad E.El-Sabbe, " Active Power Filter with Reduced Number of Semiconductor Switches Based on Synchronous Reference Frame," IEEE Conference on Power Electronics and Renewable Energy (CPERE), 2019, Accepted.
- [2] Abdellatif M. Aboutaleb, Haitham Z. Azazi, Dina S. M.Osheba, and Awad E.El-Sabbe, "A Four-Switch Shunt Active Power Filter Based on One Cycle Control for Compensating the Currents of Three-Phase Non-Linear Load," International Journal of electronics, 2019, Under Review.
- [3] Abdellatif M. Aboutaleb, Haitham Z. Azazi, Dina S. M.Osheba, and Awad E.El-Sabbe, "Split-Capacitor Shunt Active Filter for Compensating Harmonics and unbalance in Three-Phase Four-Wire System," International Journal of electronics, 2019, Under Review.

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APPENDIX A

MITSUBISHI IGBT MODULES
CM100DY-24H
 HIGH POWER SWITCHING USE
 INSULATED TYPE

Outline Drawing and Circuit Diagram

Dimensions	Inches	Millimeters
A	3.70	94.0
B	3.150±0.01	80.0±0.25
C	1.89	48.0
D	1.18 Max.	30.0 Max.
E	0.90	23.0
F	0.83	21.2
G	0.71	18.0
H	0.67	17.0
J	0.62	16.0

Dimensions	Inches	Millimeters
K	0.51	13.0
L	0.47	12.0
M	0.30	7.5
N	0.28	7.0
P	0.256 Dia.	Dia. 6.5
Q	0.31	8.0
R	M5 Metric	M5
S	0.16	4.0

Description:
 Mitsubishi IGBT Modules are designed for use in switching applications. Each module consists of two IGBTs in a half-bridge configuration with each transistor having a reverse-connected super-fast recovery free-wheel diode. All components and interconnects are isolated from the heat sinking baseplate, offering simplified system assembly and thermal management.

- Features:**
- Low Drive Power
 - Low $V_{CE(sat)}$
 - Discrete Super-Fast Recovery Free-Wheel Diode
 - High Frequency Operation
 - Isolated Baseplate for Easy Heat Sinking

- Applications:**
- AC Motor Control
 - Motion/Servo Control
 - UPS
 - Welding Power Supplies

Ordering Information:
 Example: Select the complete part module number you desire from the table below -i.e. CM100DY-24H is a 1200V (V_{CES}), 100 Ampere Dual IGBT Module.

Type	Current Rating Amperes	V_{CES} Volts (x 50)
CM	100	24

Sep.2000

MITSUBISHI IGBT MODULES

CM100DY-24H

HIGH POWER SWITCHING USE
INSULATED TYPE

Absolute Maximum Ratings, $T_J = 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ unless otherwise specified

	Symbol	Ratings	Units
Junction Temperature	T_J	-40 to 150	$^\circ\text{C}$
Storage Temperature	T_{stg}	-40 to 125	$^\circ\text{C}$
Collector-Emitter Voltage (G-E SHORT)	V_{CES}	1200	Volts
Gate-Emitter Voltage (C-E SHORT)	V_{GES}	± 20	Volts
Collector Current ($T_C = 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)	I_C	100	Amperes
Peak Collector Current	I_{CM}	200*	Amperes
Emitter Current** ($T_C = 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)	I_E	100	Amperes
Peak Emitter Current**	I_{EM}	200*	Amperes
Maximum Collector Dissipation ($T_C = 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $T_J \leq 150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)	P_c	780	Watts
Mounting Torque, M5 Main Terminal	-	1.47 ~ 1.96	N · m
Mounting Torque, M6 Mounting	-	1.96 ~ 2.94	N · m
Weight	-	270	Grams
Isolation Voltage (Main Terminal to Baseplate, AC 1 min.)	V_{Bo}	2500	Vrms

*Pulse width and repetition rate should be such that the device junction temperature (T_J) does not exceed T_{Jmax} rating.

**Represents characteristics of the anti-parallel, emitter-to-collector free-wheel diode (FWD).

Static Electrical Characteristics, $T_J = 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ unless otherwise specified

Characteristics	Symbol	Test Conditions	Min.	Typ.	Max.	Units
Collector-Cutoff Current	I_{CES}	$V_{CE} = V_{CES}$, $V_{GE} = 0\text{V}$	-	-	1.0	mA
Gate Leakage Current	I_{GES}	$V_{GE} = V_{GES}$, $V_{CE} = 0\text{V}$	-	-	0.5	μA
Gate-Emitter Threshold Voltage	$V_{GE(th)}$	$I_C = 10\text{mA}$, $V_{CE} = 10\text{V}$	4.5	6.0	7.5	Volts
Collector-Emitter Saturation Voltage	$V_{CE(sat)}$	$I_C = 100\text{A}$, $V_{GE} = 15\text{V}$	-	2.5	3.4**	Volts
		$I_C = 100\text{A}$, $V_{GE} = 15\text{V}$, $T_J = 150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	-	2.25	-	Volts
Total Gate Charge	Q_G	$V_{CC} = 600\text{V}$, $I_C = 100\text{A}$, $V_{GE} = 15\text{V}$	-	500	-	nC
Emitter-Collector Voltage	V_{EC}	$I_E = 100\text{A}$, $V_{GE} = 0\text{V}$	-	-	3.5	Volts

** Pulse width and repetition rate should be such that device junction temperature rise is negligible.

Dynamic Electrical Characteristics, $T_J = 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ unless otherwise specified

Characteristics	Symbol	Test Conditions	Min.	Typ.	Max.	Units
Input Capacitance	C_{ies}		-	-	20	nF
Output Capacitance	C_{oes}	$V_{GE} = 0\text{V}$, $V_{CE} = 10\text{V}$	-	-	7	nF
Reverse Transfer Capacitance	C_{res}		-	-	4	nF
Resistive	Turn-on Delay Time	$V_{CC} = 600\text{V}$, $I_C = 100\text{A}$,	-	-	250	ns
	Rise Time		t_r	-	-	350
Switching	Turn-off Delay Time	$V_{GE1} = V_{GE2} = 15\text{V}$, $R_G = 3.1\Omega$	-	-	300	ns
	Fall Time		t_f	-	-	350
Diode Reverse Recovery Time	t_{rr}	$I_E = 100\text{A}$, $dI_E/dt = -200\text{A}/\mu\text{s}$	-	-	250	ns
Diode Reverse Recovery Charge	Q_{rr}	$I_E = 100\text{A}$, $dI_E/dt = -200\text{A}/\mu\text{s}$	-	0.74	-	μC

Thermal and Mechanical Characteristics, $T_J = 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ unless otherwise specified

Characteristics	Symbol	Test Conditions	Min.	Typ.	Max.	Units
Thermal Resistance, Junction to Case	$R_{th(j-c)}$	Per IGBT	-	-	0.16	$^\circ\text{C}/\text{W}$
Thermal Resistance, Junction to Case	$R_{th(j-c)}$	Per FWDI	-	-	0.35	$^\circ\text{C}/\text{W}$
Contact Thermal Resistance	$R_{th(c-f)}$	Per Module, Thermal Grease Applied	-	-	0.065	$^\circ\text{C}/\text{W}$

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MITSUBISHI IGBT MODULES

CM100DY-24H

HIGH POWER SWITCHING USE
INSULATED TYPE

Sep 2000

MITSUBISHI IGBT MODULES

CM100DY-24H

HIGH POWER SWITCHING USE
INSULATED TYPE

Sep.2000

APPENDIX B

Gate driver circuit

The required gate signals for the power devices in the switching matrix are generated from dspace card. These gates signals are connected to the IGBT through gate driver circuits. This circuit is based on optocoupler device. This optocoupler is a very high speed optocoupler with a typical 50 and 12 ns rise time and fall time respectively. The propagation delay time for both high and low level outputs is 45 ns. Therefore, it is very suitable for matrix converter applications it must be taken into account that output signal of the optocoupler is inverted.

The drive circuit consist of four stages, first stage is 7407 that used as a buffer.

Second one is 4049 invert that used to invert the pulse and its pin out is shown below.

Third stage is 4N37 optocoupler that when pulse is high on input no.1 of the optocoupler , phototransistor is on and leg 5,4 is connected so a 5 volt is connected to the last stage so that the transistor become on . the pulse of 0 volt is at the output . when there is no pulse at optocoupler transistor is off and a pulse of 15 volt is at output.

ARABIC SUMMARY

ملخص الرسالة

إن الاتجاه الى توصيل الاحمال المختلفه إلى مصادر الطاقة عن طريق دوائر الكترولنيات القوى يتزايد يوما بعد يوم. هذه الدوائر تعمل كمحاولات الكترولونية لجعل الشيكه الكهربية تناسب الاحمال المختلفه و تمثل هذه الدوائر المصادر الرئيسيه للتوافقيات و الطاقة الغير فعاله فى الشيكه الكهربية. أيضا وجود الأحمال أحادية الوجه فى الأنظمة ثلاثيه الأوجه يسبب كثير من المشاكل. و هذا بسبب التيارات الغير متزنة التى تسحبها هذه الأحمال. وجود هاتان المشكلتان فى أنظمة القوى يؤثر بشده على الأداء العام للشيكه الكهربية و يقلل من جودة القدره.

نتيجة التطور السريع فى مجال إلكترونيات القوى و دوائرها، ظهر المرشح الفعال و تطور و أصبح تطبيق عملى يصلح للشيكات الكهربية. تم استخدام المرشح الفعال فى حل مشاكل التوافقيات و القدرات الغير فعاله، أيضا يمكن استخدامه لحل مشكلة عدم إتران تيارات الشيكه و جعلها متزنة جهة المصدر.

لا تزال المرشحات الفعاله غاليه نظرا لاستخدام مفاتيح إلكترونيه بترددات قطع عاليه. كثير من المجهودات تمت فى الفترة الأخيرة لتقليل تكلفه المرشح الفعال، أحدها هو تقليل عدد المفاتيح الاكترونيه (IGBT) من 6 مفاتيح إلى 4 مفاتيح. هذا التعديل يتطلب تعديل شكل DC-Link بتقسيم المكثف إلى مكثفين مع جعل نقطه منتصف المكثفات تعمل كطرف ثالث لتعويض الوجه الثالث. بالتالى تتطلب دوائر التحكم تعديلات لتناسب هذا التعديل فى دائرة القوى. و ايضا فى المرشحات الفعاله يستخدم المرشح الفعال ذو المكثف المقسم لتقليل عدد المفاتيح الاكترونيه. فى هذه الرساله تمت دراسة الأحمال المتزنة و الغير متزنة مع المرشح الفعال مع تعديل دوائر التحكم المستخدمه لتناسب التعديل فى دائرة القوى.

بالنسبة للأحمال المتزنة تم استخدام المرشح الفعال ذو الأربعة مفاتيح اعتمادا على التحكم بأسلوب الدورة الواحدة (one cycle control). تم عمل التحليل الرياضى المطلوب لتعديل دائرة التحكم لتناسب التحكم جهود المكثفين فى طرف DC بدلا من جهد مكثف واحد، و تم اثبات هذه النتائج الرياضيه بالمحاكاة عن طريق برنامج الماتلاب و تم اثبات هذه النتائج عمليا. يمتاز هذا الاسلوب من التحكم بعدم الحاجه لحساب تيارات مرجعيه، بساطة دائرة التحكم، تقليل عدد الحساسات و المفاتيح الاكترونيه، و تقليل عدد الملفات الحثيه فى خرج المرشح.

بالنسبة للأحمال الغير متزنة تم استخدام المرشح الفعال ذو المكثف المقسم اعتمادا على نظرية النموذج التزامنى الدوار (d-q theorem) لمعالجة مشاكل عدم الاتزان فى التيارات و التوافقيات الناتجة عن وجود أحمال غير خطية و غير متزنة فى الشيكه. تم عمل التعديلات اللازمه فى دائرة التحكم لملائمة دائرة القوى. و تم اثبات التعديلات رياضيا و بالمحاكاة و عمليا.

وتحتوى الرساله على أربعة فصول يمكن تلخيصها كما يلي:

الفصل الأول:

يتضمن مقدمه عن مشاكل جودة التغذية الكهربية و المرشحات كأحد حلولها. و يتضمن أيضا عن تصنيف المرشحات إلى المرشحات فعاله و المرشحات المنفعلة و المرشحات المختلطة.

الفصل الثاني:

يتضمن دراسة المرشح الفعال ذو الأربعة مفاتيح المستخدم فى تعويض الأحمال الغير خطية المتزنة. تم تعديل دائرة التحكم المعتمدة على نظرية الدورة الواحدة لتناسب التحكم فى جهد مكثفين فى DC-link. تم التعديل بالاثبات الرياضى و تم اثبات ذلك بالمحاكاة و بإستخدام نموذج عملى تم بناؤه.

الفصل الثالث:

يتضمن دراسة المرشح الفعال من نوع المكثف المقسم المستخدم فى تعويض الأحمال الغير خطية الغير المتزنة. تم إجراء التعديلات فى دائرة التحكم المعتمدة على نظرية النمذج التزامنى الدوار لتناسب التحكم فى جهد مكثفين فى DC-link. تم التعديل بالاثبات الرياضى و تم اثبات ذلك بالمحاكاة و تم إختبار الأداء الحقيقى للنظام عمليا و مقارنته مع النتائج التحليلية و وجد التوافق بينهما.

الفصل الثالث:

يقدم هذا الفصل استنتاجات العمل الحالى والعمل المستقبلى الذى يمكن القيام به على نفس المرشحات الفعالة.

تطوير أحد تقنيات التحكم في المرشح الفعال

رسالة مقدمة من

المهندس / عبداللطيف محمد عبداللطيف أبوطالب

للحصول على درجة ماجستير العلوم الهندسية (هندسة القوى و الآلات الكهربائية)
من قسم الهندسة الكهربيه

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كلية الهندسة بشبين الكوم
جامعة المنوفية
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تطوير أحد تقنيات التحكم في المرشح الفعال

رسالة مقدمة من

المهندس / عبداللطيف محمد عبداللطيف أبوظالب

للحصول على درجة ماجستير العلوم الهندسيه (هندسه القوى و الالات الكهربيه)
من قسم الهندسه الكهربيه

تحت اشراف

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أستاذ الكترولنيات القوى و تطبيقاتها المتفرغ بكلية الهندسة - جامعة المنوفية
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